

Interview with Singer and Voice Actress Uki Satake at FicZone 2025

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Uki Satake —佐武宇綺, Tokyo, 1992— is a versatile Japanese artist with great potential, known for her work as a singer, actress, and seiyū —voice actress—. For several years, she was part of the idol group 9nine, balancing her music career with appearances on television and in film.

Besides her vocal and dance skills, she enjoys drawing, practises swimming, and can play the double bass.

Her charisma and vocal talent, which the CoolJapan.es team witnessed in person, have also led her to stand out in the anime world, where she has voiced characters in titles such as *Mob Psycho 100* —Subomi Takane and Satake— and Lisa in *Lazarus*. Moreover, since 2012, she has hosted her own radio show, *Satake Uki no Uchū wo Kirei ni Suru Radio*, where she showcases her approachable and playful side.

In this exclusive interview for CoolJapan.es, conducted during FicZone 2025, we spoke with Satake about her career as a seiyū, her artistic passions, and her vision of entertainment.

A candid and cheerful conversation with one of the most beloved voices in contemporary Japan.

Interview with Uki Satake

Cool Japan: Your radio show has been on air for over a decade. What does that weekly connection with listeners mean to you?

Uki Satake: I've been doing it for about ten years, so it's incredible. I have many listeners who know who I am, and it's amazing how they understand me even if I don't speak much. I'm really grateful for this, and the rehearsals are rushed [Satake refers to singing her songs live on the programme, sometimes almost spontaneously]. So, it feels like I'm talking to family, very comfortably.

Cool Japan: You've voiced very different characters, such as QT in *Space Dandy* or Tsubomi in *Mob Psycho 100*; also in *Uzumaki*, a horror anime by Junji Itō, as Kirie. Which role has been the most challenging for you?

Uki Satake: Of all of those, *Uzumaki* was the hardest. Horror roles in general. The tricky part is the spiral of the horror genre itself, present in this work [referring to the spiral curse in the story, which obsesses the characters and brings them doom].

In horror roles, there are two parts: one is being the one who scares, and the other is the one who suffers the attack. I had to portray what it felt like to be afraid. Since I am the one who is scared, I have to scream all the time [she screams jokingly]. Normally, in everyday life, it's not like this, which makes it more difficult [laughs].

IDEA, a character from *Carole & Tuesday*, also voiced by Uki Satake.

Cool Japan: You have also voiced non-human characters or even AIs —artificial intelligences—, such as the rabbit Aladdin in *Carole & Tuesday*. How do you approach that type of performance?

Uki Satake: Speaking specifically about that series, I was watching it and there was a rabbit soft toy... And I thought: “what is this? What is this cute thing I’m seeing?” When you look at the character, you think it’s cute and fun... but inside it has a bad temper, it’s sarcastic and arrogant, and I tried to convey that duality with my voice. It’s quite scary. I recorded it with the voice I had in mind for it.

Cool Japan: Which professional would you like to work with, or work with again?

Uki Satake: Not from my seiyū work specifically, but I came to Spain for the first time after starting with the group 9nine. This time I perform as Satake, but there are people in Spain who say they like 9nine’s songs, so I want to return here with the group to perform the band’s songs and dance.

Cool Japan: What differences do you notice between singing as yourself and lending your voice to a character who sings?

Uki Satake: There are differences in that kind of work and the feelings it gives you, but both singing and performing as a character, or lending your voice to one, require the same thing: to bring out my voice.

But when you sing and dance in front of an audience, the voice and your performance reach them directly, whereas in dubbing, it comes afterwards.

Despite these differences, I enjoy both jobs. I listen to client and fan feedback later on social media. When I attend events abroad, like this one [FicZone], they tell me directly, and I hear their reactions live, but in animation this comes afterwards. So, in that sense, it's completely different, although I have no preference for one over the other. I like both, but I knew I was a singer from the beginning, so I love that.

Cool Japan: What message would you like to give to your followers in Europe who may know you through various media?

Uki Satake: I love Europe! Especially Spain —there are so many flowers and it smells of flowers! A few days ago I was walking around on my own and I noticed it. It's perfect for me. I want to work hard so I can come to Europe, and do work that people in Europe enjoy, whether dubbing or music.

Uki Satake —bottom right— alongside fellow 9nine members Sayaka Nishiwaki —top left—, Hirona Murata —top right—, and Kanae Yoshii —bottom left—.

Acknowledgements

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We even asked Satake for a greeting for CoolJapan.es, and she kindly recorded one for us —you can find it by following this link to the video platform YouTube!

Sources

- **Texts consulted from:** FicZone official website, Anime News Network | **Interview conducted by:** Andrés Domenech Alcaide [CoolJapan.es] | **Interview interpreted by:** Michie Yamaya
- **Images sourced from:** FicZone official website, Anime News Network, Official X account of Uki Satake

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